

2-TOM, 2-SON
THE IMPORTANCE OF SCHOLARSHIPS CREATED FOR FEMALE
STUDENTS

Sobirova Asilabonu Aziz kizi

Student of the 3rd English faculty, UzSWLU

Tashkent/Uzbekistan

+998973112503

Annotation: This article is about the activity of women and girls in the field of science and different opportunities created for them. Women scholars who are educators of the nation's future plays an important role in forming the foundations of the third renaissance in New Uzbekistan.

Keywords: president scholarship, state scholarships named after Alisher Navai and Islam Karimov, special scholarship named after Alexander Feinberg, Rector's scholarship, Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

In connection with the declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Youth and Business Support," many doors are opening for the young people of Uzbekistan. Based on the the state policy on youth No. 361 of 2016, a plethora of golden opportunities are being created for the future generation. Today, the educational opportunities available to young people, particularly for women, are incomparable, as women scientists are educators of the nation's future. Besides, a knowledgeable woman is considered a mirror of society. Suppose we pay considerable attention to the education of females, which in turn leads to advances in the development of science in new Uzbekistan. At the beginning of the 20th century, the enlightener of our nation, Abdulla Avlani, wrote: "Girls should strive for education more than anyone else because with this knowledge they will educate the next generation" [2].

In the resolution "Science, technology and innovation for development" adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 22, 2015, February 11 was announced as International Women's Day in the field of science. Since 2016, this day has been widely celebrated in the world. This decision was aimed at creating equal conditions for the full use of science by women and girls, as well as expanding the rights and opportunities of women. Its main ideas are the introduction of innovations, demonstration, aspiring to the top, encouragement, and support.

Today, the participation of women in scientific research is recorded in different numbers across multinational countries. For example, according to the data of the UNESCO Institute of Statistics, as of 2020, the share of scientists engaged in science worldwide is 30% (in particular, this indicator is 63% in Bolivia, 26% in France, and

2-TOM, 2-SON

8% in Ethiopia). The fact that this indicator has approached 39% in Uzbekistan is gratifying for us. This occasion stems from the available chances for females in our country and the wise usage at the right time. As a vivid example, we can cite the state paying the contract fees of women who want to continue their master's degree after the bachelor's degree. In addition, it is another gratifying fact that students of higher educational establishments in the field of pedagogy can get a job in educational institutions and improve their skills from the 2nd grade of university.

Moreover, one of the basic conveniences for the young generation is the total compensation of the examination expenses of applicants under 30 years of age who have achieved high results in the exams determining the level of the international language. Due to the focus on learning foreign languages, applicants are admitted to the institution of higher education without entrance exams through language certificates; students are continuing their master's and doctoral studies. Two hundred students with the highest scores in full-time undergraduate entrance exams starting from the 2021-2022 academic year by the measures to support young people recommended for students in higher education institutions of the Republic according to the presidential decrees dated July 6, 2021, I think that the introduction of the Presidential Grant of the Republic of Uzbekistan for young people, financed from the state budget, is one of the most outstanding achievements of young people [3].

Awarding talented young people of the Cabinet of Ministers and according to Decision No. 226 on financial incentives, undergraduate education of higher education institutions to the students at universities following scholarships were introduced: President Scholarship of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state scholarships, and special scholarships named after famous writers and the regulations on their appointment were approved. These scholarships are accessible in most universities of our country. We can take Uzbekistan State World Languages University as an example. One of the top universities in the country is Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, which provides a wide range of academic programs, including master's, Ph.D., undergraduate, graduate, and certificate programs, including national and international scholarships for both professor-teachers and students. The educational options connected to Uzbekistan State University of World Languages are shown below, giving you access to gain:

➤ **President Scholarship of the Republic of Uzbekistan;**

The President scholarship is awarded to only one student from undergraduate students of the Higher Education Institution. This scholarship is intended for the

2-TOM, 2-SON

university's Ph.D., graduate, and bachelor's students of the university. Candidates to gain the scholarship must study with excellent grades, have at least two published works (articles, theses, or works), actively participating in conferences (competitions) on the directions, know the history of Uzbekistan, information technologies, the state language, and one foreign language. The scholarship is awarded for one year starting September 1, strictly observing the specified amount (2 191 541 soum). Holders of the scholarship are accepted to study on the basis of an additional state grant without entrance exams for the master's degree in the relevant specialty within two years after completing the bachelor's degree [4].

➤ **State scholarships named after Alisher Navai and Islam Karimov;**

State scholarships are only for undergraduate students in the last two years of study. For example, 3-4 courses in 4-year education. In Uzbekistan State World Languages University, fifteen students for the Navai scholarship and one student for Islam Karimov scholarship can be candidates. Candidates to gain the scholarship must study with excellent grades, have at least two published works (articles, theses, or works), active participation in conferences (competitions) on the directions, know the history of Uzbekistan, the state language, and one foreign language. The scholarship is awarded for one year starting September 1, strictly observing the specified amount (1 461 028 soum). Holders of the scholarship are accepted to study on the basis of an additional state grant without entrance exams for the master's degree in the relevant specialty within a year after completing the bachelor's degree.

➤ **Special scholarship named after Alexander Feinberg;**

Special scholarship and badge Life of Alexander Feinberg at UzSWLU and research in the direction of studying his work, covering his activities, scientific research, and promotion in order to encourage teachers and students who have shown particular activity is established. The special scholarship quota is based on the number of faculties at UzSWLU, the faculty allocates each individually. The special scholarship is for full-time students of the 1st-3rd stage of bachelor's degree and 1st stage of master's degree at UzSWLU who meet the following criteria:

- Studying the life and work of Alexander Feinberg, covering his activities, scientific research, and conducting research in the direction of promotion;
- Show active participation in the direction of widespread promotion of literature and reading;
- Participating in conferences (competitions) on literature and reading;
- Existence of published articles (works).

2-TOM, 2-SON

Applicants to the faculty council for preliminary review by March 20 of each year submit the following documents:

- Extract from the test book (mastery indicator);
- letter of recommendation of the department;
- creative (scientific) work, its annotation and review (if available);
- tutor feedback;
- Alexander Feinberg's life and work and activities (in mass media, materials on promotion in social networks and others);
- Alexander Feinberg's life, work, and activities of the republic and scientific articles of individual authorship, published in international journals, were held a document confirming active participation in conferences (original copy);
- an international or republican exhibition, biennale, festival in one's field, participation and results in symposiums, competitions, and other prestigious events (available if any) a confirmation document.

The selection committee conducts a test and an interview with applicants until April 20 every year; by April 25, the final selection of candidates by secret ballot consists of the applicant and the commission that participated in voting for his work when two-thirds of its members vote in favor of this candidate, a special scholarship recommends for appointment; on a recommendation for the position of a special scholarship by April 27 submits the decision to the University Council. The scholarship is awarded for one year starting September 1, strictly observing the specified amount (1 461 028 soum).

➤ **Rector's Scholarship.**

Overall, there are 45 places to gain this scholarship for bachelor's and master's degree students. The scholarship is for students in the 2nd-4th stage of bachelor's degree and 2nd stage of master's degree at UzSWLU who meet the following criteria:

- Candidates must study specialization subjects with excellent grades or up to a maximum of 20% 4;
- Owing achievements and scientific publications in the field (two scientific articles and three theses);
- Having a national or international certificate of foreign language proficiency at the C1 level;
- Perfect knowledge of Uzbekistan's history and the state language.

All things considered, our President, Shavkat Mirziyoev pays considerable attention to women and their education, many normative legal acts aim to improve

2-TOM, 2-SON

this field. Numerous chances we have enumerated above were a part of the opportunities at one university of Uzbekistan. Golden opportunities like these are a lot in our country, and we feel proud that our students are utilizing them, which in turn is leading youth to the degree of scholars and scientists.

REFERENCES:

1. Rustamov H. (2023). Davlat stipendiyalari: erishish omillari. O'zbekiston talabasi, **10(11)**, 8-12.
2. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/olima-ayol--millat-tarbiyachisi>
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5320582>
4. <https://lex.uz/acts/-1399382>
5. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/olima-ayol--millat-tarbiyachisi>
6. <https://instat.uz/uz/>
7. <https://oliygoh.uz/post/prezident-stipendiyasi>

